

Beyond degradation: LC-HRMS based tracking of transformation products and toxicity during photocatalytic removal of ceftazidime via advanced oxidation processes

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ABSTRACT

High-resolution mass spectrometry combined with liquid chromatography (LC-HRMS) was employed to comprehensively investigate transformation pathways and transformation products (TPs) formation during the degradation of ceftazidime (CAZ). The degradation of CAZ was investigated using advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), including heterogeneous TiO₂ photocatalysis, MOF-based photocatalysis, and homogeneous treatments with hydrogen peroxide (HP) or persulfate (PS). TiO₂-mediated photocatalysis achieved complete CAZ removal within 60 min, with reaction rates enhanced by increased catalyst loading or oxidant addition, whereas excessive HP concentration slowed degradation. MOF-based photocatalysis showed limited activity, although oxidants improved reaction kinetics. Homogeneous photocatalytic treatments also efficiently degraded CAZ, with higher iron or oxidant concentrations accelerating the process. LC-HRMS analysis enabled the confident elucidation of eighteen TPs, seventeen of which are reported here for the first time for ceftazidime degradation, classified as N-alkylated pyridinium derivatives, aminothiazole-ring derivatives, and alkyl sulfates. Accurate-mass measurements and HRMS-based structural interpretation revealed key transformation pathways during CAZ oxidation. Total organic carbon (TOC) measurements indicated superior mineralization with TiO₂, followed by homogeneous treatments. ECOSAR-based toxicity predictions suggested low ecotoxicity for most TPs, except the parent compound and TP273, which exhibited potential toxicity toward *Daphnia magna*. Overall, photocatalytic AOPs effectively degrade CAZ and its TPs, with HRMS-supported TP elucidation demonstrating that TiO₂-based heterogeneous photocatalysis providing the highest mineralization and lowest predicted ecotoxicity.

1. Introduction

Antibiotics can be included in the list of the great discoveries of the 20th century since they have been widely used for the treatment of infections from bacteria and consequently improved and extended the quality of life [1]. However, the antibiotic consumption has been constantly increasing worldwide especially in the low income and middle-income countries thus causing implications for the antimicrobial resistance spread. In fact, the misuse or the overuse of the antibiotics can be considered responsible for the emergence and proliferation of antibiotic resistant bacteria (ARB) and antibiotic resistant genes (ARGs) [2]. Antibiotics find their way to the water cycle through consumption since

50–80% of the applied dose is excreted unaltered through urine and feces [3]. It is noteworthy that out of 100 different kinds of antibiotics used, almost 70 different kinds are detected in environmental matrices [4]. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are considered major sources of pharmaceutical contamination in the environment, as these compounds are only partially removed by conventional wastewater treatment processes [5].

Consequently, there is an urgent need for the implementation of sustainable and cost-effective treatment techniques. Advanced Oxidation processes (AOPs) which are based on the chemical, photochemical, or the photocatalytic generation of highly reactive hydroxyl radicals have been successfully applied for the elimination of these contaminants

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[6]. Moreover, a plethora of studies are here to manifest also the efficiency of another sub-category AOPs which are based on the production of sulfate radicals and are labeled as SR-AOPs [7]. The produced radicals (hydroxyl or sulfate) attack unselectively the organic contaminants causing their degradation and finally their mineralization. These processes present various advantages such as low selectivity, high reaction rates, high mineralization capacity and low environmental footprint with limited secondary pollution.

In recent years, liquid chromatography coupled with high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) has emerged as a powerful analytical tool for investigating the fate of emerging contaminants during advanced oxidation processes [8]. Owing to its high mass accuracy, resolving power, and sensitivity, LC-HRMS enables the non-target and suspect screening, confident identification, and structural elucidation of transformation products formed during contaminant degradation [9]. Unlike conventional target-based approaches that focus solely on parent compound removal, LC-HRMS allows comprehensive assessment of transformation pathways, intermediate formation, and potential persistence of transformation products, which is essential for evaluating the environmental relevance, efficiency and safety of applied treatment technologies [10–12]. Consequently, LC-HRMS-based analysis is increasingly recognized as a key component in advanced oxidation studies for assessing contaminant fate and identifying known and unknown transformation products.

In this study, the degradation of Cefazidime (CAZ), a third-generation cephalosporin antibiotic has been examined by applying and comparing different AOPs and SR-AOPs techniques. Cephalosporins account for the 50–70% of the total amount of human antibiotics due to their wide antibacterial spectrum and strong bactericidal ability [13]. CAZ is one of the most frequently used β -lactam antibiotics usually applied for serious community-acquired and nosocomial infections. CAZ presents low biodegradability and has been previously detected at concentrations up to $5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in treated hospital wastewater effluent [14]. The survival of CAZ at WWTPs effluents can in this way present an increased risk for disseminating ARB pathogens into the environment.

Up to now, various AOPs like electro-Fenton [15–17] electro-catalytic oxidation [18,19] electrochemical oxidation [20] or photocatalysis with novel synthesized catalysts [21–23] have been applied for the elimination of CAZ from aqueous solutions. However, conventional photocatalytic systems such as TiO_2 photocatalysis, photo-Fenton processes under simulated solar irradiation, and their comparison with sulfate-radical-based AOPs have not been systematically investigated for CAZ degradation. In this context, the present study aims to provide a comprehensive evaluation of multiple photocatalytic and radical-based oxidation systems for CAZ removal, while also investigating transformation product formation using LC-HRMS together with mineralization and ecotoxicity assessment. Particular emphasis is placed on the identification and structural elucidation of transformation products, eighteen of which are reported for the first time for ceftazidime degradation. This approach goes beyond conventional kinetic analysis of the parent compound, incorporating mineralization as well as *in vivo* and *in vitro* toxicity to provide a comprehensive and environmentally relevant evaluation of the applied processes. Consequently, heterogeneous photocatalysis using TiO_2 or Metal Organic Frameworks (MOF) as catalysts have been tested and compared with homogenous techniques based on photo-Fenton reaction under simulated solar irradiation (SSI). Moreover, the addition of different oxidants (H_2O_2 and $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$) was also evaluated providing by this way many different oxidizing systems. Namely, the oxidative systems SSI- TiO_2 , SSI- TiO_2 - H_2O_2 , SSI- TiO_2 - $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, Degradation were evaluated on the degradation of CAZ and the objectives were: i) to address the degradation kinetics, ii) to evaluate the addition of oxidants, iii) to identify and elucidate transformation products using LC-HRMS, iv) to record the evolution profiles of the formed TPs, v) to study the mineralization of CAZ, vi) to study the detoxification of the treated solution (on the crustacean *Daphnia magna*), and finally vii) to evaluate the toxicity of the

formed TPs using the ECOSAR software.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and reagents

CAZ (99%) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Germany). Stock solutions of the target compound were prepared in ultrapure water and kept at -20°C . Working solutions were prepared prior to illumination experiments with 10 mg/L of CAZ as initial concentration.

The catalysts employed for heterogeneous photocatalysis were Titanium dioxide P25 (Evonik, Darmstadt, Germany) and Basolite F300 (Fe-BTC, iron 1,3,5-benzenetricarboxylate MOF, BASF). P25 TiO_2 consists of approximately 80% anatase and 20% rutile, with a specific surface area of $\sim 56 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and a particle size of 20–30 nm. The coexistence of anatase and rutile phases promotes efficient charge separation and enhances photocatalytic activity, while the band gap energy is approximately 3.0–3.2 eV, corresponding to absorption in the UV region. Basolite F300 exhibits a surface area of $1300\text{--}1600 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and a bulk density of $0.16\text{--}0.35 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. It is an iron-based metal-organic framework composed of Fe^{3+} nodes coordinated with 1,3,5-benzenetricarboxylic acid (BTC) linkers, forming a highly porous structure with high adsorption capacity and good thermal stability. The material was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich/Merck (Germany). Since commercially available catalysts were used, their physicochemical properties were obtained from the manufacturer's specifications and relevant literature. Both catalysts are chemically and thermally stable under the reaction conditions used. In a previous study [24], no significant leaching of Fe from Basolite F300 was observed under comparable photocatalytic conditions. While reusability was not assessed in this work, literature reports indicate that both P25 and Fe-BTC MOFs can be reused multiple times without substantial loss of activity or stability.

Hydrogen peroxide (HP) (H_2O_2 , 30% w/v) was obtained from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) while potassium persulfate (PS) ($\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, 99 +%) from Chem-LabNV (Zedelgem, Belgium), respectively. For the analysis, LC-MS-grade methanol was purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), and formic acid (HCOOH) from Sigma Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany).

2.2. Photocatalytic experiments

The photolytic and photocatalytic treatment of CAZ solutions was carried out in an Atlas Suntest CPS+ (Linsengericht Germany) photo-reactor supplied with a xenon lamp (1500 W) operated at light intensity of 500 W m^{-2} while a glass filter restricted the transmission below 290 nm. For the heterogeneous photocatalysis, the working solution of the target compound ($C_0=10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) was initially added to the pyrex reactor and mixed with the appropriate amount of catalyst under magnetic stirring, for 30 min in the dark, in order to examine the possibility of the adsorption of CAZ on the surface of the applied catalyst. Then, the lamp was turned on and the photocatalytic treatment initiated. In the case of homogeneous photocatalysis, the pH was initially adjusted to $\text{pH} = 3$, before the addition of the iron salt in order to ensure Fe^{2+} dissolution. After the addition of the oxidants, the aqueous CAZ solution was irradiated and samples were withdrawn from the reactor during treatment, centrifuged, filtered, and then proceeded for analysis.

2.3. Analytical procedures

2.3.1. CAZ determination and TPs identification

For the determination of CAZ concentration and the identification of the formed transformation products (TPs), a Vanquish UHPLC system coupled to a benchtop Q Exactive™ Focus Orbitrap high-resolution mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) equipped with an Ion Max heated electrospray ionization (HESI-II) source was employed and operated in positive electrospray ionization (ESI⁺). For

the analysis a Thermo Hypersil GOLD C18 aQ column (50 × 2.1 mm, 1.9 μm), and the mobile phase consisted of (A) water LC-MS (0.1% formic acid) and (B) methanol (0.1% formic acid). The chromatographic separation was performed using a gradient elution program with a total run time of 15 min, under the following conditions. The mobile phase composition was initially set at 10% B and delivered at a flow rate of 0.200 mL min⁻¹, which was maintained for 1.5 min. The gradient was then increased to 60% B at 4.0 min and to 70% B at 8.0 min. Subsequently, the mobile phase was ramped to 100% B at 11.0 min and maintained until 13.0 min. Finally, the system was returned to 10% B at 14.0 min, with the flow rate increased from 0.200 to 0.350 mL min⁻¹ for column re-equilibration until 15.0 min. LC conditions are presented in detail in Tables S1 and S2.

High-resolution mass spectrometric analysis was performed using a data-dependent acquisition (Full MS/ddMS²) method operated in ESI⁺ mode. Full-scan MS spectra were acquired at a resolving power of 35,000 (FWHM) over an *m/z* range of 50–700. Data-dependent MS/MS (ddMS²) experiments were performed in discovery mode at a resolving power of 17,500, using an isolation window of 1.5 *m/z*. Stepped normalized collision energies (NCE) of 20, 35, and 60 were applied. The AGC target was set to 2 × 10⁵, with a maximum injection time of 100 ms. Up to five precursor ions were selected per scan cycle for fragmentation, using an apex trigger of 2–5 s. Isotopic peaks were excluded from MS/MS selection, and spectra were acquired in centroid mode. The HESI-Orbitrap MS/MS conditions are shown in more detail in Table S3.

Finally, Xcalibur 4.1 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, MA, USA) was used for instrument control, data acquisition, and processing of LC-HRMS data, including peak detection of TPs, molecular formula assignment, and support of structural elucidation. TPs were initially detected using full-scan MS. Subsequently, an inclusion list of the identified precursor ions was generated to enable efficient targeted fragmentation via data-dependent MS/MS (dd-MS²). In addition, an inclusion list based on TPs reported in the literature was applied to ensure MS/MS acquisition of previously known CAZ-related TPs, while full-scan HRMS acquisition enabled the detection of additional, potentially unknown compounds.

2.3.2. Mineralization studies

In order to estimate the extent of mineralization, TOC measurements were conducted using a Shimadzu TOC-L analyzer with non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) detector. The measurements of the inorganic ions release were conducted with cuvette tests and a multiparameter spectrometer (Hanna instruments).

2.3.3. Toxicity studies

The toxicity of CAZ and its arising TPs was estimated by employing both *in vivo* and *in silico* methods. Concerning *in vivo* bioassays, *D. Magna* was selected for the target organism based on the OECD 202 guideline for testing of chemicals and using a commercial kit (Standard Operational Procedures of Daphtokit, Microbiotest, Belgium). The test is based on the visual estimation of the immobilization of the crustacean *D. magna* caused by the action of possible toxicants. The ephippia were incubated for 72 h at 20 ± 1 °C under light (6000 lx) in an ISO matrix medium which was previously aerated and pH adjusted (pH=7). The same medium was also employed for control samples. Twenty neonates (aged < 24 h) per sample were employed separated in groups of 5. Each group was added in 10 mL of the irradiated sample and placed on a multi-well plate (4 wells per sample) for 24 h and 48 h of exposure times. The immobilization of the daphnids was noted after direct observation and the crustaceans that exhibited no movement after 15 s of gentle agitation were considered dead and were counted. The results were finally expressed as % effect of the immobilization percentage.

For the *in silico* estimation of the toxicity ECOSAR software (ecological structure-activity relationship model), developed by the US EPA (MS-Windows Version 2.0) was employed assessing the toxicity of parent compound and its TPs to aquatic biota (fish, daphnids, and green

algae). Acute toxicity values (LC50) (for fish and daphnid) and EC50 (for green algae), and chronic toxicity values (ChV), were calculated based on a quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) type program and the results were classified according to the criteria set by Regulation No. 1272/2008/EC [25].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Preliminary study

Prior to the application of the AOPs, photolytic treatment of the target compound was conducted in order to assess solely the effect of the irradiation on the decomposition of CAZ. In Fig. 1 the photolytic degradation of CAZ is depicted.

As observed, the photo-degradation of CAZ proceeds at a very slow rate, achieving only a 58% reduction of its initial concentration after six hours of irradiation. Moreover, hydrolytic studies conducted in the dark showed that no decomposition of CAZ occurred within the same period, and consequently, the observed decomposition can be attributed to its interaction with light. This is in agreement with previous studies showing that CAZ, and cephalosporins in general, can undergo photo-transformation [26,27].

3.2. Heterogenous photocatalysis

3.2.1. Photocatalysis with TiO₂

3.2.1.1. Effect of catalyst's concentration. The photocatalytic degradation of the selected antibiotic was investigated using TiO₂ P25 as a catalyst. Prior to illumination, the solution was stirred in the dark for 30 min in the presence of the photocatalyst to assess potential adsorption of CAZ onto the catalyst surface, which was found to be less than 5%, indicating negligible interaction in the dark. Upon reaching adsorption equilibrium, the lamp was switched on, initiating photocatalytic degradation. The results are presented in Fig. 2, which illustrates the degradation profiles of CAZ at different catalyst concentrations. The data clearly demonstrate that the presence of TiO₂ significantly accelerates the degradation of the antibiotic compared to the absence of the catalyst.

Experiments were conducted using TiO₂ concentrations ranging from 15 to 100 mg L⁻¹ while keeping the initial antibiotic concentration constant. The corresponding rate constants are summarized in Table 1. An increase in TiO₂ concentration enhanced the degradation rate, likely due to the greater availability of active sites on the catalyst surface and/or the increased generation of reactive species in solution. Based on these observations, a concentration of 50 mg L⁻¹ was selected as the working catalyst concentration for the remainder of the study.

Fig. 1. Photolytic degradation of CAZ in the absence of catalyst or any AOP chemical.

Fig. 2. Photocatalytic degradation of CAZ in the presence of different concentrations of TiO_2 ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$).

Table 1

Kinetic parameters (rate constants k (min^{-1}), regression coefficients R^2 , and half-lives $t_{1/2}$ (min)) of the selected antibiotics calculated by their photocatalytic degradation in the presence of different concentrations of TiO_2 P25 ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$).

C_{catalyst} (mg L^{-1})	k (min^{-1})	R^2	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
15	0,021	0,96	33,0
30	0,030	0,99	23,1
50	0,082	0,99	8,5
100	0,238	0,96	2,9

3.2.1.2. *Effect of oxidants.* The addition of an oxidant into a semiconductor suspension has been proven to enhance the photodegradation rate of a variety of organic pollutants [28,29]. In our study the addition of two different oxidants, hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) (HP) and peroxydisulfate potassium ($\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$)(PS) at different concentrations, was examined (Fig. 3). The corresponding kinetic parameters are summarized in Table 2.

It is obvious that addition of a small amount of HP (in our case 50 mg L^{-1}) increases the photodegradation rate. This enhancement is attributed to the generation of additional hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$),

Table 2

Kinetic parameters (rate constants k (min^{-1}), regression coefficients R^2 , and half-lives $t_{1/2}$ (min)) of CAZ photocatalytic degradation in the presence of P25 TiO_2 and different concentrations of HP or PS ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $C_{\text{catalyst}} = 50 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$).

C_{oxidant} (mg L^{-1})	HP			PS		
	k (min^{-1})	R^2	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	k (min^{-1})	R^2	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
0	0.082	0.99	8.5	0.082	0.99	8.5
50	0.095	0.96	7.3	0.088	0.96	7.9
100	0.042	0.95	16.5	0.121	0.97	5.7
200	0.029	0.98	23.9	0.122	0.97	5.7

which are highly reactive oxidizing species responsible for the degradation of ceftazidime. HP can be activated by light irradiation or by capturing the photogenerated electrons from the photocatalyst, producing the additional hydroxyl radicals according to the following equations [30]:

However, addition of higher concentrations leads to the opposite effect, decreasing the reaction rate. At elevated concentrations, HP may act as a scavenger of photogenerated holes or hydroxyl radicals, reducing the availability of reactive species for CAZ degradation [30]. Therefore, an optimal oxidant concentration is required to maximize photocatalytic efficiency.

Similarly, the addition of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ to the photocatalytic system also enhances the reaction rate. Persulfate can be activated by photo-generated electrons or by UV irradiation, producing sulfate radicals ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$), which are strong oxidizing agents capable of attacking organic molecules such as ceftazidime. The relevant reactions are [30,31]:

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ traps the photogenerated electron, preventing the recombination with the positive hole and at the same time produces the sulfate radical, which is a very strong oxidizing agent (reduction potential of $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ $E_0 = 2.6 \text{ V}$). Photo-activation also takes place producing radicals.

Fig. 3. Photocatalytic degradation of ceftazidime in the presence of P25 TiO_2 and different concentrations of A) HP ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $C_{\text{catalyst}} = 50 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) and B) PS.

Unlike hydrogen peroxide, high concentrations of peroxydisulfate were not detrimental to the reaction rate, although increasing the concentration from 100 to 200 mg L⁻¹ resulted in only a slight improvement in the degradation kinetics. In summary, hydroxyl (•OH) and sulfate (SO₄•⁻) radicals generated in the photocatalytic systems are considered the primary oxidative species responsible for the degradation of ceftazidime and the formation of its transformation products.

3.2.2. Photocatalysis with MOF

3.2.2.1. Primary degradation. In the case of MOF-based photocatalysis CAZ solution was also left in the dark for 30 min prior to illumination in order to examine the potential of adsorption on the catalyst's surface. The obtained results showed that the target compound was not adsorbed on MOF's surface. After the passage of 30 min, the light was turned on and the photocatalytic degradation of CAZ was recorded. The results are depicted in Fig. 4. Obviously, the efficiency of MOF as a photocatalyst is rather limited since much slower reaction rates are achieved compared to P25 TiO₂. After 120 min of treatment only 65% reduction is achieved. The reduced efficiency can be attributed to the fast recombination of the photogenerated electron-hole pairs [24].

3.2.2.2. Addition of oxidants. Previous studies demonstrated that addition of oxidants can promote the photocatalytic efficiency of MOF photocatalysts. This can be attributed to the oxidants ability to prohibit the fast recombination of the generated electrons and holes and to offer additional oxidative radicals through their light-activation or through their activation by iron, when iron based MOFs are employed, in a Fenton type reaction [32].

Consequently, the effect of two types of oxidants was examined employing three different concentrations 50 mg L⁻¹, 100 mg L⁻¹ and 200 mg L⁻¹ and the obtained results are depicted in Fig. 5.

Obviously, an enhancement of the process is observed with the addition of HP. Higher concentrations of the oxidant causes larger improvement of the photocatalytic process. Addition of 200 mgL⁻¹ of HP achieves the higher reaction rate and leads to almost complete degradation of CAZ within two hours of treatment. In Table 3 the calculated kinetic parameters are presented.

Accordingly, addition of PS in the photocatalytic treatment increases significantly the reaction rate. Increase of the amount of the oxidant added causes a further improvement of the photocatalytic rate. Addition of 200 mgL⁻¹ PS achieves the highest degradation yield, > 99% after two hours of irradiation.

3.3. Homogenous photocatalysis

3.3.1. Primary degradation

In case of homogenous photocatalysis, experiments were conducted using either HP in photo-Fenton type reactions or PS in photo-Fenton

Fig. 4. Photocatalytic degradation of CAZ in the presence of MOF. $C_{0drug} = 10\text{mgL}^{-1}$, $C_{catalyst} = 100\text{mgL}^{-1}$.

like reactions. In Fig. 6 the photocatalytic degradation of CAZ in the presence of $[\text{Fe}^{2+}] = 1\text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $[\text{HP/PS}] = 100\text{ mg L}^{-1}$ are presented.

Obviously, the degradation of the target compound proceeds slower than heterogenous photocatalysis. Both oxidants demonstrate similar effect with HP being slightly more efficient. Calculation of the kinetic parameters yielded $k = 0.02\text{ min}^{-1}$ in the presence of HP and 0.018 min^{-1} for PS.

3.3.2. Effect of iron concentration

In order to examine the effect of iron on the degradation of CAZ, experiments were conducted under different concentrations of Fe^{2+} ions. The obtained results are depicted in Fig. 7, while in Table 4 the calculated kinetic parameters are presented.

Obviously, by increasing the amount of Fe^{2+} in the solution, higher reaction rates are achieved since ferrous ions are the main species that can activate the oxidants to produce hydroxyl/sulfate radicals [33].

3.3.3. Effect of concentration of the oxidants

The effect of the amount of oxidants on the degradation of CAZ was also examined by conducting experiments using 50, 100 or 200 mg L⁻¹ HP or PS. The obtained results are depicted in Fig. 8, while in Table 5 the calculated kinetic parameters are presented.

In the two sets of experiments opposite observations are recorded. In case of HP, increase of the amount of the oxidant causes a decrease in the reaction rate while in the case of PS, higher amount of oxidant appears to accelerate the reaction rate. This is in agreement with the aforementioned result concerning heterogenous photocatalysis with TiO₂, where high amounts of HP were detrimental to the degradation kinetics of CAZ due to scavenging effects. On the contrary, for PS, high amounts of the oxidant were beneficial in all applied AOPs.

3.4. Mineralization studies

The extend of mineralization achieved using different AOPs was evaluated by TOC measurements. In Fig. 9 the reduction of TOC during treatment with different processes is presented. The applied systems were a) TiO₂, b) MOF-HP, c) MOF-PS, d) Fe^{2+}/HP and e) Fe^{2+}/PS . The efficiency of the heterogenous photocatalysis with MOF catalyst on the mineralization of CAZ was evaluated only in the presence of oxidants since without their addition the applied catalyst exhibited poor degradation efficiency.

Obviously, the highest mineralization is achieved in heterogenous photocatalysis, with TiO₂ as catalyst, since a 58% reduction of TOC is observed after three hours of treatment. Homogeneous photocatalysis with HP as oxidant achieves also high mineralization, with 51% reduction of TOC in same time frame. When using PS, lower mineralization is achieved (36%) while with heterogenous photocatalysis with MOF catalyst only a slight decrease of TOC (18% and 10%) was recorded in the presence of HP and PS respectively, indicating that more prolonged irradiation time is required.

The observed differences in TOC reduction among the applied AOPs highlight the varying efficiencies of different oxidation pathways in achieving complete mineralization. The superior performance of TiO₂ in heterogeneous photocatalysis can be attributed to its high photocatalytic activity, effective charge separation, and ability to generate hydroxyl radicals (•OH) under irradiation. The significant reduction in TOC suggests that TiO₂ facilitates the breakdown of CAZ into smaller organic intermediates, which are further oxidized into CO₂ and H₂O.

Homogeneous photocatalysis with HP as an oxidant also demonstrated a high degree of mineralization indicating the strong oxidative potential of hydroxyl radicals generated via HP photolysis. In contrast, the lower TOC reduction observed in the presence of PS can be linked to differences in radical generation pathways. Sulfate radicals (SO₄•⁻) generated from PS activation exhibit different reaction kinetics compared to hydroxyl radicals, potentially leading to slower degradation or accumulation of organic by-products that resist further

Fig. 5. Photocatalytic degradation of ceftazidime in the presence of MOF and different concentrations of H_2O_2 ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $C_{\text{catalyst}} = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$).

Table 3

Kinetic parameters (rate constants k (min^{-1}), regression coefficients R^2 , and half-lives $t_{1/2}$ (min)) of CAZ photocatalytic degradation in the presence of MOF and different concentrations of H_2O_2 or Persulfate ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $C_{\text{catalyst}} = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$).

Oxidant (mg L^{-1})	HP			PS		
	k (min^{-1})	R^2	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	k (min^{-1})	R^2	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
0	0.009	0.99	77.0	0.009	0.99	77.0
50	0.017	0.99	40.8	0.026	0.99	26.7
100	0.022	0.99	31.5	0.033	0.98	21.0
200	0.030	0.99	23.1	0.037	0.99	18.7

Fig. 6. Photocatalytic degradation of ceftazidime in the presence of Fe^{2+} and different oxidants ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $[\text{Fe}^{2+}] = 1 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $[\text{HP/PS}] = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{pH} = 3$).

oxidation.

The low mineralization efficiency observed with MOF-based catalysts suggests that while these materials may facilitate CAZ degradation, they do not effectively promote complete mineralization within the tested timeframe. This could be due to limited light absorption or to insufficient radical generation. The need for prolonged irradiation time indicates that catalyst modifications may be required to enhance their effectiveness.

3.5. Toxicity evaluation

The incomplete mineralization observed in the applied systems

raises concerns regarding the formation of potentially toxic intermediates. Therefore, toxicity evaluation is essential in order to assess the environmental safety of the treated water. In this context, both experimental toxicity tests and *in silico* predictions were used to evaluate the potential ecological impact of CAZ degradation and the formation of its transformation products.

The data obtained from the applied toxicity test at the end of each process are depicted in Fig. 10. As observed, the immobilization effect on *Daphnia* in the untreated CAZ solution is 25% and 50%, measured at 24 h and 48 h, respectively. Treatment with TiO_2 causes a significant reduction in toxicity, lowering the immobilization effect to 10% and 25%, respectively. Similar results were observed for the homogeneous treatment process with HP, which also causes a slight reduction in toxicity, whereas the system with PS maintains the immobilization effect at levels similar to those of the untreated solution.

On the contrary, the heterogeneous systems with the MOF catalyst lead to a remarkable increase in toxicity levels (100%). Comparison with the TOC measurements reveals that the three systems (TiO_2 , Fe^{2+}/HP , and Fe^{2+}/PS), which achieve a notable degree of mineralization, also contribute to a decrease in toxicity. In contrast, the MOF-based photocatalytic processes, which exhibited negligible mineralization, resulted in a significant increase in toxicity levels. This suggests that these systems lead to the formation of intermediate compounds that persist during the photocatalytic process and exhibit higher toxicity than the parent compound. This observation aligns with previous studies that have shown photolysis of cephalosporin antibiotics with negligible mineralization can lead to increased toxicity [27,34]. Furthermore, the experimental toxicity results are consistent with the ECOSAR predictions discussed in 3.8, indicating that certain transformation products formed during the treatment may retain or increase their toxic potential toward aquatic organisms. Taken together, these findings highlight the importance of evaluating not only the degradation efficiency of advanced oxidation processes but also the evolution of toxicity during treatment in order to ensure the environmental safety of the treated effluents.

3.6. LC-HRMS based TPs identification and structural elucidation

Identifying the TPs formed during the photocatalytic treatment of ceftazidime is essential for accurately assessing and optimizing the process. In many cases, pharmaceutical TPs are more persistent or even more toxic than their parent molecules, as already observed in the previous section when MOF based photocatalysis was applied. Therefore, understanding how ceftazidime transforms under photocatalytic

Fig. 7. Photocatalytic degradation of CAZ in the presence of different concentrations of Fe^{2+} and A) HP and B) PS. ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $[\text{HP/PS}] = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{pH} = 3$).

Table 4

Kinetic parameters (rate constants k (min^{-1}), regression coefficients R^2 , and half-lives $t_{1/2}$ (min)) of CAZ photocatalytic degradation in the presence of different concentrations of Fe^{2+} and HP or PS. ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $[\text{HP/PS}] = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{pH} = 3$).

Fe^{2+} (mg L^{-1})	HP			PS		
	k (min^{-1})	R^2	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	k (min^{-1})	R^2	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
1	0.020	0.99	34.7	0.018	0.98	38.5
2	0.023	0.99	30.1	0.033	0.99	21.0
5	0.044	0.99	15.8	0.065	0.98	10.7

treatment and evaluating the toxicity of the resulting TP mixture are critical steps.

The TPs were characterized using the high-resolution capabilities of the Q-Exactive Focus Orbitrap system. Initial TP screening was based on precise mass measurements of pseudo-molecular ions detected in positive or negative ionization mode during full-scan analysis. To confirm these findings and elucidate structural features, MS/MS experiments were carried out to obtain high-accuracy fragmentation spectra (mass error < 5 ppm). Most of the detected TPs eluted earlier than ceftazidime, indicating the formation of more polar or hydrophilic species. Accurate mass data from HRMS, together with MS/MS fragmentation patterns and spectral comparison to the parent molecule, were used to tentatively assign elemental formulas and propose structures for the detected TPs. Furthermore, the identification confidence of the TPs was evaluated according to the classification framework proposed by Schymanski et al.

[35] TPs supported by diagnostic MS/MS fragments and literature comparison were classified as Level 2b (probable structure), whereas those with less extensive structural evidence were assigned to Level 3 (tentative candidate structure) or Level 4 (unequivocal molecular formula). The corresponding identification confidence levels are summarized in Tables S4 and S5.

Tables S4-5 provide an overview of the TPs detected across all photocatalytic experiments, together with their corresponding MS fragmentation data and the assigned identification confidence levels. Fig. 11 illustrates several key characteristic fragments of ceftazidime, which were also considered in the structural assignment of the generated TPs.

Eighteen TPs were identified following the photocatalytic treatment, including five classified as Level 2b, nine as Level 3 and four as Level 4. These compounds can be grouped into three main structural categories:

Table 5

Kinetic parameters (rate constants k (min^{-1}), regression coefficients R^2 , and half-lives $t_{1/2}$ (min)) of CAZ photocatalytic degradation in the presence of different concentrations of Fe^{2+} and HP or PS. ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $[\text{Fe}^{2+}] = 2 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{pH} = 3$).

oxidant (mg L^{-1})	HP			PS		
	k (min^{-1})	R^2	$t_{1/2}$ (min)	k (min^{-1})	R^2	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
50	0.03	0.99	23.1	0.026	0.99	26.6
100	0.023	0.99	30.1	0.033	0.99	21.0
200	0.012	0.99	57.8	0.048	0.99	14.4

Fig. 8. Photocatalytic degradation of ceftazidime in the presence of Fe^{2+} and different concentrations of oxidants: a) HP and b) PS. ($C_{0(\text{drug})} = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $[\text{Fe}^{2+}] = 2 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{pH} = 3$).

Fig. 9. TOC reduction of ceftazidime's solutions during the application of different AOPs.

(1) N-alkylated pyridinium derivatives, (2) aminothiazole-ring derivatives, and (3) alkyl sulfates. Furthermore, their formation appears to involve multiple and often concurrent reaction pathways, including hydroxylation, progressive oxidation of the hydroxylated intermediates, decarboxylation, dealkylation processes, as well as cleavage of C–N and C–S bonds. These mechanisms collectively illustrate the complexity of the photocatalytic transformation route and highlight the propensity of the parent compound to undergo both stepwise oxidative transformations and bond-scission reactions under the applied treatment conditions.

In Fig. 12, the identified TPs are presented. A total of twelve compounds belonging to the category of the N-alkylated pyridinium derivatives were identified, three of which were classified as Level 2b and nine as Level 3 identifications. Their assignment was supported by the presence of the characteristic fragment ion of the pyridinium moiety at m/z 80.0495, which is also observed in the fragmentation pattern of the parent compound.

These derivatives were formed via cleavage of adjacent C–C or C–N bonds in close proximity to the pyridinium ring, while subsequent hydroxylation, oxidation, and dealkylation reactions led to the generation of a diverse set of compounds within this category. Since all identified transformation products retained the intact m/z 80.0495 fragment, as observed in the parent compound, hydroxylation/oxidation is inferred to have occurred on the aliphatic side chain rather than on the pyridinium ring.

In particular, TPs 164, 152, and 168 are considered to be carboxylic acids, as their MS fragmentation spectra exhibited a characteristic neutral loss of 46 Da ($-\text{CO}_2$), indicative of carboxylic acid functionalities, yielding fragment ions at m/z 118.0651, 106.0657, and 122.0606,

respectively.

With respect to the aminothiazole-ring derivatives, only one transformation product (TP) was detected, designated as TP273 (Level 2b identification). This specific TP was formed through cleavage of the C–N bond linking the aminothiazole moiety to the β -lactam ring. The presence of the characteristic fragment ion at $m/z = 126.0120$, which is also observed in the fragmentation pattern of the parent compound, confirms the retention of the aminothiazole ring and supports the proposed structure. Notably, is the only TP identified in the present study that has been previously reported as a degradation by-product of ceftazidime during electro-Fenton and electrocatalytic oxidation [15,18]. However, two geometric isomers of TP273 were detected in our study, resulting from the carbon–nitrogen double bond in the aminothiazolyl-oxime side chain. The Z-isomer corresponds to the biologically active form incorporated into the parent antibiotic to ensure β -lactamase stability, whereas the E-isomer was also observed as a transformation product. Oxidative conditions, such as those applied in this study, can promote the interconversion between these isomers of TP273 by affecting the stability of the oxime C=N bond, leading to the detection of both forms during chromatographic analysis.

Finally, four alkyl-sulfates derivatives, designated as TP164, TP165, TP250, and TP280, were detected and exhibited highly similar MS/MS fragmentation behavior in negative ionization mode. In all cases, the spectra were dominated by the characteristic sulfate-related fragment ions at $m/z = 79.9574$ (SO_3^-) and 96.9601 (HSO_4^-), which are diagnostic of sulfate-type functionalities [36]. Additional low-mass fragment ions further indicated extensive oxidative degradation and fragmentation of the parent ceftazidime molecule, with no retention of recognizable

Fig. 11. Characteristic fragments produced in the MS spectra of CAZ.

Fig. 10. Changes in toxicity (% immobilization effect at 24 and 48 h) after photocatalytic treatment of CAZ solution with different AOPs.

Fig. 12. Proposed transformation pathway of ceftazidime and corresponding TPs identified by HRMS. Blue: *N*-alkylated pyridinium derivatives, Pink: aminothiazole derivatives, and Green: aliphatic sulfates. Arrows indicate the proposed transformation sequence.

structural moieties such as the aminothiazole or pyridinium groups. Based on the consistent presence of these sulfate-specific fragments and the absence of core-related ions, these transformation products were grouped and classified as alkyl sulfate-like sulfur-containing

compounds. However, due to the lack of structure-specific fragment ions and the limited information provided by MS/MS alone, their exact molecular structures, including the precise bonding environment and substitution position of the sulfate group, could not be unambiguously

Fig. 13. Time profiles of the most abundant TPs in the first 60 min of treatment in different oxidation processes. Dashed lines correspond to the right axis (except MOF/PS system).

elucidated. Consequently, these transformation products are reported only at the level of their molecular formulas and were therefore classified as Level 4 identifications according to the employed framework.

3.7. Time-profiles of the identified TPs

To achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the main photocatalytic transformation pathways, the evolution profiles of the TPs formed during treatment were investigated based on the peak areas obtained from LC analysis (Fig. 13). A comparison of peak areas was also performed to identify the most prevalent TPs in each treatment process; however, this approach should be regarded as semi-quantitative due to the absence of reference standards and potential differences in analytical response among compounds.

As can be observed, TP138 is the most abundant transformation product across all investigated processes, exhibiting the highest relative concentration. Its formation is detected within the first minutes of the reaction, while its concentration remains elevated for up to the first 60 min of treatment. This behavior is consistent with its position in the proposed transformation pathway depicted in Fig. 12, as TP138 corresponds to one of the most extensively dealkylated N-alkylated pyridinium derivatives identified in this study.

In contrast, transformation products such as TP136 are formed exclusively during the initial minutes of the treatment and subsequently diminish. The majority of the remaining TPs show an increasing trend during the first 60 min of reaction or reach a plateau, indicating their relative persistence under the applied treatment conditions.

3.8. Toxicity prediction of the identified TPs

The potential ecotoxicity of the identified transformation products (TPs) was predicted using the ECOSAR (Ecological Structure Activity Relationships) model, with the estimated toxicity levels summarized in Table 7. ECOSAR was employed to evaluate acute toxicity toward representative aquatic organisms, providing insight into the environmental relevance of the detected TPs. According to the predicted values, the majority of the transformation products exhibit negligible toxicity, indicating a generally low ecotoxicological risk associated with the

transformation products. Notably, only the parent compound and TP273 were predicted to exhibit toxicity toward *Daphnia magna*, while no significant toxicity was estimated for the remaining TPs.

This observation is particularly noteworthy, as it suggests that the degradation of the parent antibiotic predominantly leads to the formation of less toxic by-products, a finding that is in good agreement with the results obtained from the *Daphnia magna* bioassays, where a clear reduction in toxicity was observed over the course of treatment. In Fe-based systems, overall toxicity decreased compared to initial values, and the minor increases observed at certain time points are considered not significant, indicating that the Fe catalysts themselves do not substantially contribute to toxicity. In contrast, an increase in toxicity was recorded during the experiments involving MOF-based processes. Importantly, TP273 was detected exclusively under these specific experimental conditions, which may account for the observed increase in toxicity. TP273 has been associated with the presence of an aminothiazole ring, a structural motif that has been reported in previous studies to confer enhanced toxicity toward aquatic organisms, particularly *Daphnia magna*. Such structural features may enhance the interaction of the molecule with biological targets, potentially increasing its toxicological impact. It is therefore plausible that TP273 acts either directly as a toxicant or as a precursor for the formation of additional aminothiazole-containing derivatives, which may further contribute to the elevated toxicity observed. Potential synergistic effects with minor transformation products in MOF-based systems cannot be excluded. This hypothesis is further supported by the fact that, in these MOF-based processes, no significant reduction in total organic carbon (TOC) was achieved, indicating limited mineralization and the persistence of organic intermediates that may sustain or enhance ecotoxic effects. Taken together, the ECOSAR predictions and the experimental bioassay results indicate that the photocatalytic degradation of ceftazidime generally leads to the formation of transformation products with lower toxicity than the parent compound, although specific intermediates such as TP273 may locally increase ecotoxicity under certain treatment conditions, highlighting the importance of coupling degradation studies with toxicity assessment.

Table 7

Predicted acute and chronic toxicity of Ceftazidime and its TPs.

Compounds	Acute toxicity (mg/L) (EC ₍₅₀₎ /LC ₍₅₀₎)			Chronic toxicity (mg/L) (ChV)		
	Fish	Daphnids	Green algae	Fish	Daphnids	Green algae
Ceftazidime	171000	42	395	1067	6.5	518
TP138	2.33*10 ⁸	7.66*10 ⁷	5.98*10 ⁶	1.2*10 ⁷	1.64*10 ⁶	464000
TP186	5.0*10 ⁶	1.79*10 ⁶	195000	283000	47908	18218
TP136	28553	1415	9653	1593	291	4774
TP183	547000	7.91*10 ⁶	5150	33.8	11083	458
TP163	42383	2904	7165	13338	139	1595
TP193	99719	6481	17752	36866	295	3806
TP197	2.06*10 ⁶	104000	450000	2.5*10 ⁶	3803	81820
TP152	1.97*10 ⁷	7.26*10 ⁶	910000	1.16*10 ⁶	213000	91200
TP164	1.07*10 ⁷	4.06*10 ⁶	578000	651000	130000	62006
TP168	1.68*10 ⁸	5.66*10 ⁷	4.86*10 ⁶	8.87*10 ⁶	1.29*10 ⁶	398000
TP273	45520	20.8	158	277	2.48	216
TP165	502000	197000	32271	6936	3734	617000
TP154	13639	6284	1973	1041	342	324

Not harmful
Harmful
Toxic
Very toxic

4. Conclusions

All applied advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) demonstrated the capability to degrade the target antibiotic CAZ, albeit with varying efficiencies. Heterogeneous photocatalysis using TiO₂ proved to be the most effective treatment, achieving complete degradation of CAZ within 60 min. An increase in catalyst loading resulted in enhanced reaction kinetics, while the addition of oxidants further improved degradation performance. However, excessive hydrogen peroxide (HP) concentrations exerted an inhibitory effect, likely due to radical scavenging, whereas higher persulfate (PS) doses consistently accelerated the degradation process.

In contrast, MOF-based photocatalysis exhibited limited effectiveness toward CAZ degradation under the examined conditions. Nevertheless, the introduction of oxidants substantially enhanced the reaction rate, an effect attributed to the suppression of electron-hole recombination and the additional generation of reactive oxidative species. Homogeneous photocatalytic processes employing HP or PS also achieved efficient CAZ degradation, with increasing iron or oxidant concentrations leading to accelerated reaction rates.

A total of eighteen transformation products (TPs) were identified during CAZ degradation and classified into three major structural categories: (i) N-alkylated pyridinium derivatives, (ii) aminothiazole-ring derivatives, and (iii) alkyl sulfates. The formation and evolution of these TPs provided valuable insight into the underlying transformation pathways and confirmed the prevalence of dealkylation, hydroxylation and oxidation across all the investigated AOPs.

Total organic carbon (TOC) measurements highlighted the superior mineralization efficiency of TiO₂-based heterogeneous photocatalysis, followed by homogeneous photocatalytic systems. Conversely, MOF-based processes exhibited negligible TOC removal, indicating limited mineralization and the persistence of organic intermediates. These findings were further supported by ecotoxicological assessment and ECOSAR-based toxicity predictions, which showed that the majority of the identified transformation products exhibited low or negligible aquatic toxicity. Only the parent compound and TP273 were predicted to be toxic toward *Daphnia magna*, with TP273 being detected exclusively in MOF-based experiments. The concurrent lack of TOC reduction and the formation of this aminothiazole-containing TP may partially explain the increased toxicity observed under these conditions.

Overall, this study demonstrates that photocatalytic AOPs—particularly TiO₂-based heterogeneous photocatalysis—are highly effective for CAZ degradation, mineralization, and toxicity mitigation. The findings underscore the importance of coupling chemical degradation with mineralization and ecotoxicological assessment to ensure environmentally safe water treatment. Future research should focus on optimizing operational parameters, exploring hybrid AOP strategies, and evaluating catalyst stability and reusability to enhance the overall efficiency and applicability of photocatalytic processes for real wastewater treatment.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Eleni Evgenidou: Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Data curation, Visualization, Supervision, Conceptualization, Writing - Original draft, **Panagiotis Pavlidis:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Validation, Data curation, **Androniki Rapti:** Formal analysis, Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Data curation, **Lelouda-Athanasia Koronaïou:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Data curation, Validation, **Vasileios Alampanos:** Methodology, Validation, Data curation, Visualization, Writing - Original draft, **Dimitra A. Lambropoulou:** Investigation, Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Resources, Project administration. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.scenv.2026.100326](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scenv.2026.100326).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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